

Some Results on Generalized Multi Poly-Bernoulli and Euler Polynomials

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Abstract: The Arakawa-Kaneko zeta function has been introduced ten years ago by T. Arakawa and M. Kaneko in [22]. In [22], Arakawa and Kaneko have expressed the special values of this function at negative integers with the help of generalized Bernoulli numbers $B^{(k)}$ called *poly-Bernoulli numbers*. Kim-Kim [4] introduced Multi poly- Bernoulli numbers and proved that special values of certain zeta functions at non-positive integers can be described in terms of these numbers. The study of Multi poly-Bernoulli and Euler numbers and their combinatorial relations has received much attention [2,4,6,7,12,13,14,19,22,27]. In this paper we introduce the generalization of Multi poly-Bernoulli and Euler numbers and consider some combinatorial relationships of the Generalized Multi poly-Bernoulli and Euler numbers of higher order. The present paper deals with Generalization of Multi poly-Bernoulli numbers and polynomials of higher order. In 2002, Q. M. Luo and et al (see [11, 23, 24]) defined the generalization of Bernoulli polynomials and Euler numbers. Some earlier results of Luo in terms of generalized Multi poly-Bernoulli and Euler numbers, can be deduced. Also we investigate some relationships between Multi poly-Bernoulli and Euler polynomials.

Key Words: Generalized Multi poly-Bernoulli polynomials, generalized Multi poly-Euler polynomials, stirling numbers, polylogarithm, Multi- polylogarithm.

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§1. Introduction

Bernoulli numbers are the signs of a very strong bond between elementary number theory, complex analytic number theory, homotopy theory(the J-homomorphism, and stable homotopy groups of spheres), differential topology(differential structures on spheres), the theory of modular forms(Eisenstein series) and p-adic analytic number theory(the p-adic L-function) of

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Mathematics. For $n \in \mathbb{Z}, n \geq 0$, Bernoulli numbers B_n originally arise in the study of finite sums of a given power of consecutive integers. They are given by $B_0 = 1, B_1 = -1/2, B_2 = 1/6, B_3 = 0, B_4 = -1/30, \dots$, with $B_{2n+1} = 0$ for $n > 1$, and

$$B_n = -\frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{m=0}^{n-1} \binom{n+1}{m} B_m, \quad n \geq 1 \quad (1)$$

The modern definition of Bernoulli numbers B_n can be defined by the contour integral

$$B_n = \frac{n!}{2\pi i} \oint \frac{z}{e^z - 1} \frac{dz}{z^{n+1}}, \quad (2)$$

where the contour encloses the origin, has radius less than 2π .

Also Bernoulli polynomials $B_n(x)$ are usually defined (see [1], [4], [5]) by the generating function

$$G(x, t) = \frac{te^{xt}}{e^t - 1} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n(x) \frac{t^n}{n!}, \quad |t| < 2\pi \quad (3)$$

and consequently, Bernoulli numbers $B_n(0) := B_n$ can be obtained by the generating function

$$\frac{t}{e^t - 1} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n \frac{t^n}{n!}$$

Bernoulli polynomials, first studied by Euler (see [1]), are employed in the integral representation of differentiable periodic functions, and play an important role in the approximation of such functions by means of polynomials (see [14]-[18]).

Euler polynomials $E_n(x)$ are defined by the generating function

$$\frac{2e^{xt}}{e^t + 1} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} E_n(x) \frac{t^n}{n!}, \quad |t| < \pi \quad (4)$$

Euler numbers E_n can be obtained by the generating function

$$\frac{2}{e^t + 1} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} E_n \frac{t^n}{n!} \quad (5)$$

The first four such polynomials, are

$$\begin{aligned} B_0(x) &= 1, B_1(x) = x - 1/2, B_2(x) = x^2 - x + 1/6 \\ B_3(x) &= x^3 - 3/2x^2 + 1/2x, \dots \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} E_0(x) &= 1, E_1(x) = x - 1/2, E_2(x) = x^2 - x, \\ E_3(x) &= x^3 - 3/2x^2 + 1/4, \dots \end{aligned}$$

Euler polynomials are strictly connected with Bernoulli ones, and are used in the Taylor expansion in a neighborhood of the origin of trigonometric and hyperbolic secant functions.

In the sequel, we list some properties of Bernoulli and Euler numbers and polynomials as well as recurrence relations and identities.

$$B_n(x) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} B_k x^{n-k}, \tag{6}$$

$$E_n(x) = \frac{1}{n+1} \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} (2-2^{k+1}) \binom{n+1}{k} B_k x^{n+1-k}. \tag{7}$$

$$B_n(x+1) - B_n(x) = nx^{n-1}, \tag{8}$$

$$E_n(x+1) + E_n(x) = 2x^n. \tag{9}$$

Lemma 1.1(see[20],[21]) *For any integer $n \geq 0$, we have*

$$B_n(x+1) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} B_k(x) \tag{10}$$

$$E_n(x+1) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} E_k(x) \tag{11}$$

Consequently, from (8), (9) and lemma 1.1, we obtain,

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n+1}{k} B_k(x) = (n+1)x^n \tag{12}$$

$$\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} E_k(x) + E_n(x) = 2x^n. \tag{13}$$

Lemma 1.3 *For any positive integer $n \geq 0$, we have*

$$B_n(px) = p^{n-1} \sum_{r=0}^{p-1} B_n(x + \frac{r}{p}) \text{ (} p \text{ is a positive integer)} \tag{14}$$

$$E_n(px) = p^n \sum_{r=0}^{p-1} (-1)^r E_n(x + \frac{r}{p}) \text{ (} p \text{ is an odd integer)} \tag{15}$$

Let us briefly recall $k - th$ polylogarithm. The polylogarithm is a special function $Li_k(z)$, that is defined by the sum

$$Li_k(z) := \sum_{s=1}^{\infty} \frac{z^s}{s^k} \tag{16}$$

For formal power series $Li_k(z)$ is the $k - th$ polylogarithm if $k \geq 1$, and a rational function if $k \leq 0$. The name of the function come from the fact that it may alternatively be defined as the repeated integral of itself, namely that

$$Li_{k+1}(z) = \int_0^z \frac{Li_k(t)}{t} dt \tag{17}$$

for integer values of k , we have the following explicit expressions

$$Li_1(z) = -\log(1 - z), Li_0(z) = \frac{z}{1 - z} Li_{-1}(z) = \frac{z}{(1 - z)^2}$$

$$Li_{-2}(z) = \frac{z(1 + z)}{(1 - z)^3}, Li_{-3}(z) = \frac{z(1 + 4z + z^2)}{(1 - z)^4}, \dots$$

The integral of the Bose-Einstein distribution is expressed in terms of a polylogarithm,

$$Li_{k+1}(z) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(k + 1)} \int_0^\infty \frac{t^k}{\frac{e^t}{z} - 1} dt \tag{18}$$

Lemma 1.3(see[18]) *For $n \in N \cup \{0\}$, we have an explicit formula for $Li_{-n}(z)$ as follow*

$$Li_{-n}(z) = \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} \frac{(-1)^{n+k+1} (k - 1)! S(n + 1, k)}{(1 - z)^k} \tag{19}$$

$(n = 1, 2, \dots)$

where $s(n, k)$ are Stirling numbers of the second kind.

Now, we introduce the generalization of $Li_k(z)$. Let r be an integer with a value greater than one.

Definition 1.1 *Let k_1, k_2, \dots, k_r be integers. The generalization of polylogarithm are defined by*

$$Li_{k_1, k_2, \dots, k_r}(z) = \sum_{\substack{m_1, m_2, \dots, m_r \in \mathbb{Z} \\ 0 < m_1 < m_2 < \dots < m_r}} \frac{z^{m_r}}{m_1^{k_1} \dots m_r^{k_r}} \tag{20}$$

The rational numbers $B_n^{(k)}$, $(n = 0, 1, 2, \dots)$ are said to be poly-Bernoulli numbers if they satisfy

$$\frac{Li_k(1 - e^{-x})}{1 - e^{-x}} = \sum_{n=0}^\infty B_n^{(k)} \frac{x^n}{n!} \tag{21}$$

In addition, for any $n \geq 0$, $B_n^{(1)}$ is the classical Bernoulli number, B_n (see[7], [12]). Also, the rational numbers $H_n^{(k)}(u)$, $(n = 0, 1, 2, \dots)$ are said to be poly-Euler numbers if they satisfy

$$\frac{Li_k(1 - e^{(1-u)})}{u - e^t} = \sum_{n=0}^\infty H_n^{(k)}(u) \frac{t^n}{n!} \tag{22}$$

where u is an algebraic real number and $k \geq 1$. (see[13],[19])

Let us now introduce a generalization of poly-Bernoulli numbers, making use of $Li_{k_1, \dots, k_r}(z)$.

Definition 1.1(see[7]) *Multi poly-Bernoulli numbers $B_n^{(k_0, \dots, k_r)}$, $(n = 0, 1, 2, \dots)$ are defined for each integer k_1, k_2, \dots, k_r by the generating series*

$$\frac{Li_{(k_1, k_2, \dots, k_r)}(1 - e^{-t})}{(1 - e^{-t})^r} = \sum_{n=0}^\infty B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)} \frac{t^n}{n!} \tag{23}$$

By Definition 1.2, the left hand side of (23) is

$$\frac{1}{1^{k_1} 2^{k_2} \dots r^{k_r}} + \sum_{\substack{0 < m_1 < \dots < m_r \\ m_r \neq r}} \frac{(1 - e^{-t})^{m_r - r}}{m_1^{k_1} \dots m_r^{k_r}} \tag{24}$$

hence we have

$$B_0^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)} = \frac{1}{1^{k_1} 2^{k_2} \dots r^{k_r}} \tag{25}$$

$$B_1^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)} = \sum_{0 < m_1 < \dots < m_r} \frac{1}{m_1^{k_1} \dots m_{r-1}^{k_{r-1}} (r+1)^{k_r}} \tag{26}$$

Definition 1.3 Multi poly-Euler numbers $H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}$, $(n = 0, 1, \dots)$ are defined for each integer k_1, \dots, k_r by the generating series

$$\frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - e^{(1-u)})}{(u - e^t)^r} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(u) \frac{t^n}{n!} \tag{27}$$

Kaneko [6] presented the following recurrence formulae for poly-Bernoulli numbers which we state hear.

Theorem 1.1(Kaneko)([2,6,14,22]) For any $k \in Z$ and $n \geq 0$, we have

$$B_n^{(k)} = \frac{1}{n+1} \left\{ B_n^{(k-1)} - \sum_{m=1}^{n-1} \binom{n}{m-1} B_m^{(k)} \right\} \tag{28}$$

$$B_n^{(k)} = (-1)^n \sum_{k=1}^{n+1} \frac{(-1)^{m-1} (m-1)! \left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ m-1 \end{matrix} \right\}}{m^k} \tag{29}$$

$$B_n^{(-k)} = \sum_{j=0}^{\min(n,k)} (j!)^2 \left\{ \begin{matrix} n+1 \\ j+1 \end{matrix} \right\} \left\{ \begin{matrix} k+1 \\ j+1 \end{matrix} \right\} \quad (n, k \geq 0) \tag{30}$$

$$B_n^{(-k)} = B_k^{(-n)} \quad (n, k \geq 0) \tag{31}$$

$$B_n^{(k)} = \sum_{m=0}^n (-1)^m \binom{n}{m} B_{n-m}^{(k-1)} \left\{ \sum_{l=0}^m \frac{(-1)^l}{n-l+1} \binom{m}{l} B_l^{(1)} \right\} \tag{32}$$

where

$$\left\{ \begin{matrix} n \\ m \end{matrix} \right\} = \frac{(-1)^m}{m!} \sum_{l=0}^m (-1)^l \binom{m}{l} l^n \quad n, m \geq 0 \tag{33}$$

called the second type stirling numbers.

Y.Hamahata and H.Masubuchi in [12], presented the following recurrence formulae for Multi poly-Bernoulli numbers.

Theorem 1.2(H.Masubuchi & Y.Hamahata) For $n \geq 0$ and $(k_1, \dots, k_r \in Z)$ we have

$$B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)} = (-1)^n \sum_{m_r=r}^{n+r} \left(\sum_{0 < m_1 < \dots < m_r} \frac{(-1)^{m_r-r} (m_r - r)! \binom{n}{m_r - r}}{m_1^{k_1} \dots m_r^{k_r}} \right) \tag{34}$$

If $k_r \neq 1$ and $n \geq 1$, then

$$B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)} = \frac{1}{n+r} \left\{ B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_{r-1}, k_r-1)} - \sum_{m=1}^{n-1} \binom{n}{m-1} B_m^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)} \right\} \tag{35}$$

If $k_r = 1$ and $n \geq 1$, then

$$B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_{r-1}, 1)} = \frac{1}{n+r} \left\{ B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_{r-1})} - \sum_{m=0}^{n-1} (-1)^{n-m} \left\{ r \binom{n}{m} + \binom{n}{m-1} \right\} B_m^{(k_1, \dots, k_{r-1}, 1)} \right\} \tag{36}$$

Also, they proved (see[1]) if

$$B[r]_n^{(k)} = B_n^{(\overbrace{0, \dots, 0}^{r-1}, k)} \tag{37}$$

then for $n, k \geq 0$, we have

$$B[r]_n^{(-k)} = B[r]_k^{(-n)} \tag{38}$$

In [23], [24], Q.M.Luo, F.Oi and L.Debnath defined the generalization of Bernoulli and Euler polynomials $B_n(x, a, b, c)$ and $E_n(x, a, b, c)$ respectively, which are expressed as follows

$$\frac{t}{b^t - a^t} c^{xt} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} B_k(x, a, b, c) \frac{t^k}{k!} \tag{39}$$

$$\frac{2c^{xt}}{b^t + a^t} = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} E_k(x, a, b, c) \frac{t^k}{k!} \tag{40}$$

In this paper, by the method of Q.M.Luo and et al [11], we give some properties on generalized Multi poly-Bernoulli and Euler polynomials

Definition 1.4 Let $a, b > 0$ and $a \neq b$. The generalized Multi poly-Bernoulli numbers $B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(a, b)$, the generalized Multi poly-Bernoulli polynomials

$$B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x, a, b) \text{ and } B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x, a, b, c)$$

are defined by the following generating functions, respectively;

$$\frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - (ab)^{-t})}{(b^t - a^{-t})^r} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(a, b) \frac{t^n}{n!}, \quad |t| < \frac{2\pi}{|\ln a + \ln b|} \quad (41)$$

$$\frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - (ab)^{-t})}{(b^t - a^{-t})^r} e^{rxt} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x; a, b) \frac{t^n}{n!}, \quad |t| < \frac{2\pi}{|\ln a + \ln b|} \quad (42)$$

$$\frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - (ab)^{-t})}{(b^t - a^{-t})^r} c^{rxt} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x; a, b, c) \frac{t^n}{n!}, \quad |t| < \frac{2\pi}{|\ln a + \ln b|} \quad (43)$$

Definition 1.5 Let $a, b > 0$, and $a \neq b$, the generalized Multi poly-Euler numbers $H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(u; a, b)$, the generalized multi poly-Euler polynomial $H_n^{k_1, \dots, k_r}(x; u, a, b)$ and $H_n^{k_1, \dots, k_r}(x; u, a, b, c)$ are defined by the following generating functions, respectively,

$$\frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - e^{(1-u)})}{(ua^{-t} - b^t)^r} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(u, a, b) \frac{t^n}{n!}, \quad |t| < \frac{2\pi}{|\ln a + \ln b|} \quad (44)$$

$$\frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - e^{(1-u)})}{(ua^{-t} - b^t)^r} e^{rxt} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x; u, a, b) \frac{t^n}{n!}, \quad |t| < \frac{2\pi}{|\ln a + \ln b|} \quad (45)$$

$$\frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - e^{(1-u)})}{(ua^{-t} - b^t)^r} c^{rxt} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x; u, a, b, c) \frac{t^n}{n!}, \quad |t| < \frac{2\pi}{|\ln a + \ln b|} \quad (46)$$

§2. Main Theorems

In this section, we introduce our main results. We give some theorems and corollaries which are related to generalized Multi poly-Bernoulli numbers and generalized Multi poly-Euler polynomials. We present some recurrence formulae for generalized Multi-poly-Bernoulli and Euler polynomials.

Theorem 2.1 Let $a, b > 0$ and $a \neq b$, we have

$$B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(a, b) = B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}\left(\frac{-\ln b}{\ln a + \ln b}\right) (\ln a + \ln b)^n \quad (47)$$

proof By applying Definition 1.4, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - (ab)^{-x})}{(b^x - a^{-x})^r} &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(a, b)}{n!} x^n \\ \frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - (ab)^{-x})}{(b^x - a^{-x})^r} &= \frac{1}{b^{xr}} \left(\frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - e^{-x \ln ab})}{(1 - e^{-x \ln ab})^r} \right) \\ &= e^{-xr \ln b} \left(\frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - e^{-x \ln ab})}{(1 - e^{-x \ln ab})^r} \right) \end{aligned}$$

So, we get

$$\frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - e^{-x \ln ab})}{(b^x - a^{-x})^r} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)} \left(\frac{-\ln b}{\ln a + \ln b} \right) (\ln a + \ln b)^n \frac{x^n}{n!}$$

Therefore, by comparing the coefficients of $\frac{t^n}{n!}$ on both sides, proof will be complete

$$B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(a, b) = B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)} \left(\frac{-\ln b}{\ln a + \ln b} \right) (\ln a + \ln b)^n$$

□

The generalized Multi poly-Bernoulli and Euler numbers process a number of interesting properties which we state here

Theorem 2.2 *Let $a, b > 0$ and $a \neq b$. For real algebraic u we have*

$$H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(u; a, b) = H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)} \left(u; \frac{\ln a}{\ln a + \ln b} \right) (\ln a + \ln b)^n. \tag{48}$$

Next, we investigate a strong relationships between $B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(a, b)$ and $B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}$.

Theorem 2.3 *Let $a, b > 0, a \neq b$ and $a > b > 0$, we have*

$$B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(a, b) = \sum_{i=0}^j (-r)^{j-i} (\ln a + \ln b)^i (\ln b)^{j-i} \binom{j}{i} B_i^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}. \tag{49}$$

□

By applying Definition 1.4, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - (ab)^{-x})}{(b^x - a^{-x})^r} &= \frac{1}{b^{xr}} \frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - (ab)^{-x})}{(1 - e^{-x \ln ab})^r} \\ &= \left(\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{(\ln b)^k}{k!} x^k r^k (-1)^k \right) \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)} (\ln a + \ln b)^n \frac{x^n}{n!} \right) \\ &= \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{i=0}^j (-r)^{j-i} \frac{B_j^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)} (\ln a + \ln b)^i (\ln b)^{j-i}}{i!(j-i)!} x^j \right) \end{aligned}$$

By comparing the coefficient of $\frac{t^n}{n!}$ on both sides, we get.

$$B_j^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(a, b) = \sum_{i=0}^j (-r)^{j-i} (\ln a + \ln b)^i (\ln b)^{j-i} \binom{j}{i} B_i^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}$$

□

By the same method proceeded in the proof of Theorem 2.3, we obtained similar relations for $H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(u; a, b)$ and $H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}$.

Theorem 2.4 Let $a, b > 0$, and $b > a > 0$. For algebraic real number u , we have

$$H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(u; a, b) = \sum_{i=0}^n r^i (\ln a + \ln b)^i (\ln a)^{n-i} \binom{n}{i} H_i^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)} \quad (50)$$

Theorem 2.5 Let $x \in R$ and conditions of Theorem 2.3 holds true, then we get

$$B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x; a, b, c) = \sum_{l=0}^n \binom{n}{l} r^{n-l} (\ln c)^{n-l} B_l^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(a, b) x^{n-l} \quad (51)$$

$$H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(u; x, a, b, c) = \sum_{l=0}^n \binom{n}{l} r^{n-l} (\ln c)^{n-l} H_l^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(u; a, b) x^{n-l} \quad (52)$$

Proof By applying Definitions 1.4 and 1.5, proof will be complete. □

Theorem 2.6 Let conditions of Theorem 2.5 holds true, we obtain

$$H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(u; x, a, b, c) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} r^{n-k} (\ln c)^{n-k} H_k^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}\left(u, \frac{\ln a}{\ln a + \ln b}\right) (\ln a + \ln b)^k x^{n-k} \quad (53)$$

$$B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x; a, b, c) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} r^{n-k} (\ln c)^{n-k} B_k^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}\left(\frac{-\ln b}{\ln a + \ln b}\right) (\ln a + \ln b)^k x^{n-k}. \quad (54)$$

Proof By applying Theorems 2.1 and 2.5, we get (53), and Obviously, the result of (54) is similar with (53). □

Theorem 2.7 Let conditions of Theorem 2.5 holds true, then we get

$$B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x; a, b, c) = \sum_{k=0}^n \sum_{j=0}^k (-1)^{k-j} \binom{n}{k} \binom{k}{j} r^{n-k} (\ln c)^{n-k} (\ln b)^{k-j} (\ln a + \ln b)^j B_j^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)} x^{n-k} \quad (55)$$

$$H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x; a, b, c) = \sum_{k=0}^n \sum_{j=0}^k \binom{n}{k} \binom{k}{j} r^{n-k} (\ln c)^{n-k} (\ln a)^{k-j} (\ln c + \ln b)^j H_j^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)} x^{n-k} \quad (56)$$

$$B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x + 1; a, b, c) = B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}\left(x; ac, \frac{b}{c}, c\right) \quad (57)$$

$$H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(u, 1 - x, ac, b, c) = B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}\left(u, -x, ac, \frac{b}{c}, c\right) \quad (58)$$

$$B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x + y; a, b, c) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} r^{n-k} (\ln c)^{n-k} B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x; a, b, c) y^{n-k} \quad (59)$$

$$H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(u; x + y, a, b, c) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} r^{n-k} (\ln c)^{n-k} H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x; a, b, c) y^{n-k} \quad (60)$$

Proof We only prove (59) and (55)-(60) can be derived by Definitions 1.4 and 1.5.

$$\begin{aligned}
\frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - (ab)^{-t})}{(b^t - a^{-t})^r} c^{(x+y)rt} &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x+y, a, b, c) \frac{t^n}{n!} \\
&= \frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - (ab)^{-t})}{(b^t - a^{-t})^r} c^{xrt} \cdot c^{yrt} \\
&= \left(\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x; a, b, c) \frac{t^n}{n!} \right) \left(\sum_{i=0}^n \frac{y^i (\ln c)^i r^i}{i!} t^i \right) \\
&= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} r^{n-k} y^{n-k} (\ln c)^{n-k} B_k^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x; a, b, c) \right) \frac{t^n}{n!}
\end{aligned}$$

So by comparing the coefficients of $\frac{t^n}{n!}$ in the two expressions, we obtain the desired result 2.13.

□

Theorem 2.8 *By the same method proceeded in the proof of previous Theorems, we find similar relations for $B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(t)$ and $H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(u, t)$.*

$$B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(t) = B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(e^{1+t}, e^{-t}) \quad (61)$$

$$H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(u, t) = H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(u; e^t, e^{1-t}) \quad (62)$$

Now, we present formulae which show a deeper motivation of generalized poly-Bernoulli and Euler polynomials.

Theorem 2.9 *Let $x, y \in \mathbb{R}$ and conditions of Theorem 2.5 holds true, we get*

$$B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x, a, b, c) = (\ln a + \ln b)^n B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)} \left(\frac{-\ln b + x \ln c}{\ln a + \ln b} \right) \quad (63)$$

$$H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(u; x, a, b, c) = H_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)} \left(u; \frac{\ln a + x \ln c}{\ln a + \ln b} \right) \quad (64)$$

Proof We can write

$$\begin{aligned}
\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x; a, b, c) \frac{t^n}{n!} &= \frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - (ab)^{-t})}{(b^t - a^{-t})^r} c^{xrt} \\
&= \frac{1}{b^{rt}} \frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - (ab)^{-t})}{(1 - (ab)^{-t})^r} c^{xrt} \\
&= e^{r(-\ln b + x \ln c)t} \left(\frac{Li_{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(1 - e^{-t \ln ab})}{(1 - e^{-t \ln ab})^r} \right)
\end{aligned}$$

By comparing the coefficients of $\frac{t^n}{n!}$ on both sides, we get

$$B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x; a, b, c) = (\ln a + \ln b)^n B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)} \left(\frac{-\ln b + x \ln c}{\ln a + \ln b} \right).$$

□

GI-Sang Cheon and H.M.Srivastava in [8],[10] investigated the classical relationship between Bernoulli and Euler polynomials . Now we present a relationship between generalized Multi poly-Bernoulli and generalized Euler polynomials. The following relation (65) are given by Q.M.Luo, So by applying this recurrence formula, we obtain Theorem 2.10,

$$E_k(x + 1, 1, b, b) + E_k(x, 1, b, b) = 2x^k(\ln b)^k \tag{65}$$

Theorem 2.10 *Let $a, b > 0$, we have*

$$B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x + y; a, b) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \left[B_k^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(y, a, b) + B_k^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(y + 1, a, b) \right] r^{n-k} E_{n-k}(x, 1, b, b) \tag{66}$$

Proof We know

$$B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x + y; 1, b, b) = \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} r^{n-k} (\ln b)^{n-k} B_k^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(y; 1, b, b) x^{n-k},$$

$$E_k(x + y, 1, b, b) + E_k(x, 1, b, b) = 2x^k(\ln b)^k$$

So, we obtain

$$B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x + y, 1, b, b) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} r^{n-k} (\ln b)^{n-k} B_k^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(y; 1, b, b) \times$$

$$\left[\frac{1}{(\ln b)^{n-k}} (E_{n-k}(x; 1, b, b) + E_{n-k}(x + 1, 1, b, b)) \right]$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} r^{n-k} B_k^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(y; 1, b, b) \times$$

$$\left[(E_{n-k}(x; 1, b, b) + \sum_{j=0}^{n-k} \binom{n-k}{j} E_j(x, 1, b, b)) \right]$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} r^{n-k} B_k^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(y; 1, b, b) E_{n-k}(x; 1, b, b)$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n}{j} r^{n-k} E_j(x; 1, b, b) \sum_{k=0}^{n-j} \binom{n-j}{k} B_k^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(y; 1, b, b)$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} r^{n-k} B_k^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(y; 1, b, b) E_{n-k}(x; 1, b, b)$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2} \sum_{j=0}^n \binom{n}{j} r^{n-k} B_{n-j}^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(y + 1; 1, b, b) E_j(x; 1, b, b)$$

So we have

$$\begin{aligned} & B_n^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(x+y; a, b) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=0}^n \binom{n}{k} \left[B_k^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(y, a, b) + B_k^{(k_1, \dots, k_r)}(y+1, a, b) \right] r^{n-k} E_{n-k}(x, 1, b, b) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore we obtain the desired result (66). \square

The following corollary is a straightforward consequence of Theorem 2.10.

Corollary 2.1(see [8],[10]) *In Theorem 2.10, if we set $r = 1$, $k = 1$ and $b = e$, we obtain*

$$B_n(x) = \sum_{\substack{k=0 \\ k \neq 1}}^n \binom{n}{k} B_k E_{n-k}(x). \quad (67)$$

Further work: In [25], Jang et al. gave new formulae on Genocchi numbers. They defined poly-Genocchi numbers to give the relation between Genocchi numbers, Euler numbers, and poly-Genocchi numbers. After Y. Simsek [26], gave a new generating functions which produce Genocchi zeta functions. So by applying a similar method of Kim-Kim [4], we can introduce generalized Genocchi Zeta functions and next define Multi poly-Genocchi numbers and obtain several properties in this area.

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